

Social And Economic Life In Egypt Through The Traveling Journey Of Nasir Khusraw (437 AH / 1045 AD - 444 AH / 1052 AD)

Ibrahim Ahmad Al Shyyab, Abeer Mansour ALkhasawneh, RiyadMoflehALkhlaifat

Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 11, 2021

Accepted:
November 12, 2021

Keywords :

Nasir Khusraw, social
life in Egypt, Cairo,
Markets, Commerce

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5682267

Abstract

Nasir Khusraw in his journey (Safar Nama) gave complete and comprehensive information about an important period of the history of the Islamic world in the fifth century AH / eleventh century AD. He was interested in describing the social and economic life of many of the areas he visited, especially Egypt. He described the army and its distribution, and the trade that he described in Egypt in this period as being like a free trade zone in the world, due to its abundance of goods and the abundance of markets and merchandise brought to it from different parts of the world. He also accurately described social life in Egypt and described the security and stability that the country prevails, as he talked about Al-Azhar Mosque, Amr Ibn Al-Aas Mosque, scholars and jurists and their role in enriching the scientific life in the country. This trip represented a major source in the study of Islamic civilization in the Islamic East in that period.

Introduction

He is Abu Mu'in Hamid al-Din Nasir bin Khusraw bin Harith al-Qabadani al-Farsi. He was born in the year 394 AH/1004 AD in the town of Qabadani in the district of Marv in the Khorasan Province. (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 15, Nasir Sarwar Qabadani, 1983, p. 5, Alice Hensberger, 2003, pp. 26-27, Nasir Khusraw, 1974, p. 28-29, Zaki Muhammad Hassan, 2009, p. 21, Zaki Muhammad Hassan, 2008, p. 48)

One of the most famous Muslim travelers in the fifth century AH / eleventh century AD, he came from a middle-ranked concrete family, and he had a wide culture, he joined the service of the Ghaznavid state during the days of Muhammad al-Ghaznawi and his son Mahmoud, where he was raised Sunni in the court of the Ghaznavids, and he was responsible for the affairs of When conditions changed and the Seljuk state came, Nasir Khusraw joined the service in the court of the Seljuk ruler in Khurasan. (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 15, Nasir Khusraw Qabadani, 1983, pp. 5-6, Nasir Khusraw, 1974, p. 31).

He was very knowledgeable, he read philosophy and the opinions of Al-Farabi and Ibn Sina, and he was able to read the Qur'an and Sunnah and studied the Torah and the Gospel.

He has many books, including a collection of poetry containing thirty thousand verses of poetry, the *zad almusafirin*, the *Jami' al-Hikmatayn* and others. (Hensberger, 2003, pp. 40-41, Nasir Khusraw: 1974, p. 33)

Introducing Nasir Khusraw's Journey/ Its Motives and Objectives:

Travel literature is one of the important sources of history.

It reflects a human civilized vision, It provides the reader with a clear picture of the social and economic life of the country to which the traveler arrives, As for Nasir Khusraw's book *Safarnama*, it is translated from Persian, It was translated from Persian to French (Charles Schaeffer) in 1881 AD in Paris. Then it was published again in Berlin in 1922 AD, and Yahya al-Khashab translated it into Arabic for the first time in Cairo in 1943 AD. (Nasir Khusraw: 1974, pp. 47-48).

It is one of the oldest journeys by a Persian traveler. This journey took place between the year 437-444 AH/1045-1053 CE and lasted about seven years. It was before the journey of Ibn Battuta and Ibn Jubayr. The journey was divided into three stages:

The first stage: It begins with maru in 437 AH / 1045 AD and ends in Cairo in 439 AH / 1047 AD. At this stage, his writings were free of any political or religious purpose. Rather, he wanted to go to Mecca to perform the Hajj, and in the meantime, his desire to contact and debate with scholars appeared, and he met many of them and was interested in science and scholars.

The second stage: This is the period of his stay in Egypt, which lasted for three years and three months from the year 439-442 AH / 1047-1052 AD, in which he spoke several times about his desire not to prolong his stay in Egypt, but he drew knowledge from his sources directly and was convinced of the Fatimid doctrine, and Fatimid Egypt was abounding With knowledge and scholars, and its mosques were places for lessons of jurisprudence and Islamic philosophy, and he participated in them and became one of its teacher.

As for the third stage: It is his return to Balkh via the Hijaz, Al-Ahsa and Basra, after he became one of the most prominent men of the Fatimid da'wa, and it ends in 444 AH / 1052 AD.

As for the time of writing this trip, studies indicate that there is a difference in determining the date on which this trip was written. Some of them say that it was written before 453 AH / 1060 AD.

Some of them say that it was written after the year 455 AH/1063 AD, but it is more likely that Nasir Khusraw wrote the Safarnama immediately after his return to Khurasan, before he became an enemy of the Seljuk state because of his embrace of the Fatimid Ismaili doctrine, which he believed in and became a preacher to it. It is noticeable that the traveler Nasir Khusraw wrote his journey day by day, and this is evidenced by the accuracy in describing the places he visited in the Levant, Jerusalem, Egypt and the Arab countries. And he was honest in his writing, if he saw something, he saw it with the eye, a text on that, and if he heard about something, he narrated it and made the covenant on its narrator. (Nasir Khusraw, 1974, pp. 23-25).

One of the most important motives for this journey, as Nasir Khusraw mentions, is what he read in the Noble Qur'an in Surat Muhammad and Al-Fath. The Almighty said:(Then do they not reflect upon the Qur'an, or are there locks upon [their] hearts?) Surah Muhammad: Verse 24. This is because in the Qur'an there is what relieves distress, spreads tranquility and calmness, and conveys sound faith, then the Almighty's saying:(Certainly was Allāh pleased with the believers when they pledged allegiance to you, [O Muhammed], under the tree, and He knew what was in their hearts, so He sent down tranquility upon them and rewarded them with an imminent conquest) Surah Al-Fath: 18. And he immediately got up to go to that tree under which the believers pledged allegiance to their Prophet, and a state of confusion and loss seized him, and he mentions that the cause of this confusion and this transformation was a dream in which a man appeared to him asking him to stop drinking alcohol, but he justifies that by running away from His worries, but he tells him that comforting oneself does not come with a loss of feeling, but rather by searching for what increases the mind and wisdom, and this man points to him towards the qiblah and says (whoever finds himself) so he wakes up from his sleep and from his negligence heading to Mecca to perform the Hajj, where the journey was in (437-444 AH / 1045-1052 AD) for a period of seven years (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 19-21, and Zaki Muhammad, 2008, p. 47).

Political life in the Islamic East in the era of Nasir Khusraw:

The political life was turbulent in the Islamic East at the end of the fourth century AH, the beginning of the fifth AH, the tenth century AD, and the beginning of the eleventh century AD.

Several states became independent from the center of the Abbasid Caliphate, such as the Persian states, the Hamdanids in Aleppo and the Fatimids in Egypt and the Maghreb.

The authority of the Abbasid Caliph shrank, and he became a powerless religious leader, Meanwhile, the Shiite Buyids took control of Baghdad in 334 AH / 945 AD.

And the Shiite sultan became the protector of the Sunni caliph, and the Saffarid state was attacking the Abbasid caliph, so the Samanid state protected him, and it was in this atmosphere that Nasir Khusraw grew up and made his journey (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 11-15).

The economic and social life in Egypt as described by Nasir Khusraw in his book Safarnama:

Nasir Khusraw's talk about Egypt in his famous journey, Safarnama, was a talk of admiration and admiration, so much so that he prepared it as a model for the virtuous city headed by a ruler just, merciful, gracious to people, who does not oppress anyone, and does not covet people's money, and that is why people did not hide anything from their money, even the rich They used to offer their money to the Caliph in the days of hardship, when the Nile decreased to meet the people's livelihood (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, pp. 121-122).

As for the Minister in Egypt, he was appointed by the Fatimid Caliph, and he required asceticism, piety and reason. As for the judges, their salaries were high so that they would not covet people's money and deviate from the truth and the truth, which was reflected on the people of Egypt in the well-being of life and the people's good morals and noble qualities such as magnanimity and truth. chivalry, and honesty (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 95, 116).

Tennis City:

Nasir Khusraw described the first Egyptian city he reached, Tennis, as the first free trade city in the world.

It is crowded with people, and has two mosques and great markets, nearly ten thousand shops of perfumers, weavers and craftsmen (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 91, and Naser Khusraw, 1983, p. 83, Vozaki Mohammad Hassan, 2009, p. 22). It is also famous for making turbans that are woven from colored reeds, which are rare. As for white turbans, they are woven in the city of Damietta, and in the city of Tennis, factories for the Sultan make special fabrics that are not sold or given to anyone, until it was said that one of the Persian kings was sent to buy from the royal clothes and paid the sum of twenty A thousand but got nothing (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 92, and Naser Khusraw, 1983, p. 83). The textile industry has reached a great development, especially the manufacturers who specialize in weaving the Sultan's clothes, as they weave a fabric known as peacock or bouqlimun, a fabric that is unparalleled in the world. Its color changes during daylight hours. It contains golden threads that appear in the sun in bright colors. That period, until it is said that one of the Roman rulers sent to the Sultan in Egypt to give him the city of Tennis with a hundred Roman cities, hoping for this rare Peacock weave (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 92, and Naser Khusraw, 1983, p. 84).

Cairo city:

He began by talking about the story of the construction of Cairo, where it is mentioned that the ignorant Caliph Allah the Fatimid, who ordered its construction in 358 AH after the conquest of Egypt, and after the king of Morocco and Andalusia, sent an army to Egypt, and this army had to cross the Nile, and this is a very dangerous matter. Because the Nile is large and wide, then it is filled with crocodiles, but the Goats army was able to cross the Nile, according to the narration (Nasir Khosrow, 1983, pp. 92-93, and Nasir Khosrow Alawi, 1993, pp. 102-103).

Then he begins by describing Cairo and its public life, saying that it has five gates, The city has no wall due to its fourteen storey high buildings. It also describes the buildings in Cairo, which consist of five or six floors, As for drinking water, it was brought from the Nile to the homes. He says that in Cairo and Egypt there are fifty thousand camels, this is in addition to the bears who carry the sacks on their backs and roam the alleys and narrow lanes (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 106, Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 96, Zaki Muhammad Hassan, 2009, p. 23).

In the city of Cairo, there are many gardens and orchards that are watered from wells. In the presidential palace, there are many orchards that are watered by water mills. On the rooftops, you used to see the beautiful gardens as parks in their beauty. As for the palaces of Cairo, they were beautiful, clean, and far from each other (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 96, Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 106).

Then he describes the lanes of Cairo and says that there are ten shops or lanes in Cairo, and in the east of Cairo there is a mountain, and in it is the Ahmed Ibn Tulun Mosque, and the Sultan used to pray in it during the blessed month of Ramadan and in Friday prayers. It also describes the luxury in building palaces and buildings, and this is evidence of the active economic situation, and that the state is in an affluent way of living. He also talks about the markets crowded with pedestrians, and goods and that all these markets and the crisis were lit by lamps that never go out because the sunlight does not reach these places and narrow alleys, In the middle of the market is the Omar Ibn Al-Aas Mosque, which is decorated with columns and domes, inlaid with plates and alabaster, and on which are written a wall from the Holy Qur'an (Nasir Khusraw, 104-106, 1983 and Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 114-117).

The Nile River:

Then he begins by describing the city of Egypt, It is mentioned that he arrived on Sunday of the month of Safar in the year 439 AH, and the first thing he talks about is the Nile River, which originates in the south and passes through Cairo and ends in the waters of the Mediterranean Sea, and describes its waters as many and great, equivalent to twice the river of Gihon, and he talks about that the Sultan of Egypt sent someone to search for The source of the Nile River, and he concluded that the river stems from a mountain called Jabal al-Qamar, and when the sun is in the sign of Cancer, the floods of the Nile increase, which are about twenty cubits high (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, pp. 86-87 and Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 95-96).

One of the scientists supervises the Nile for measurements during the flood, and when the Nile flood reaches its extent, which is estimated at 18 cubits. The omens are announced, and preparations begin to celebrate the fulfillment of the Nile. It is remarkable that the Sultan of Egypt does not take the tax from the people of Egypt unless the flood of the Nile reaches a length of 18 cubits (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 97, and Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 88).

Economic life in Egypt:**1- Agriculture:**

Describes the agricultural life of the people of Egypt at the time of the flood, which lasts about forty days, rising until it reaches its extent, then remains forty days, then gradually decreases for forty days, and then the farmers begin to cultivate the lands from which the water recedes and they are saturated with water, so they do not need irrigation later (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 89, and Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 98).

It also describes the economic life that is built on the waters of the Nile River, and what is the water drainage system and the irrigation system on the Nile Basin through digging canals and basins on its sides, and extending for long distances around many villages and long countryside, and wheels that raise water to organize irrigation and drainage, and villages and cities were built On heights above the level of the valley so that it is far from drowning at the time of the flood, as he describes the means of transportation that depend on river boats, in addition to building dams during the flood season so that the water does not reach the edges of the cities, These dams were built at the expense of the state, and an amount of ten thousand Moroccan dinars was allocated to them (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 88, and Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 97-98).

2- Trade:

Then he talks about the internal trade between Alexandria and Cairo, this trade that transports by ships and boats many kinds of fruits from the port of Alexandria to Cairo. It is known that Alexandria is located on the Roman Sea (Mediterranean Sea) and the edge of the Nile River, about thirty leagues away from Cairo. In Alexandria, there is a lighthouse with large reflecting mirrors on top of it. Even if the enemy ships came from the Roman Sea, the sun's rays would shine on them from this lighthouse and burn them, which made the Romans think

about getting rid of these mirrors, so they sent someone to break them and get rid of them (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 89, and Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 98-99).

He also talked about foreign trade, especially the islands scattered in the Sea of Rum, the most important of which is the island of Sicily, where ships sail from Egypt to that island in twenty days, an island with an area of about 80 x 80 leagues, and from it a ship loaded with money comes every year because it belongs to the Sultan of Egypt. They bring fine linen and various types of clothes and ornate cloths, each dress is sold in Egypt for 10 Moroccan dinars (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 100-101, and Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 91, Mr. Abdulaziz Salem, 2001, p. 239).

Then he talks about the economic and commercial life in the city of Cairo again, and the number of shops in it is estimated at about 20 thousand, and it is a private property of the Fatimid Caliph, and its rent is between two and ten dinars per month. A house, all of which belongs to the Caliph, and is rented out monthly to the parish and the merchants.

It also describes the Caliph's Palace in the heart of Cairo, and the spacious surroundings around it, and the guards on it guarding the palace at night. Their number is estimated at a thousand-armed guards, half of them on horses and the other half as men. From afar, the palace looks like a great high mountain with high balconies. It has high walls, and this indicates the level of economic well-being that Egypt reached at that time (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, pp. 94-95, Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 104, Zaki Muhammad Hassan, 2009, p. 22, and see Zaki Muhammad Hassan, 2008, pp. 49-50)

It is noticeable that merchants in Egypt ride donkeys from their homes to their shops, and that there are a large number of donkeys for rent, They are numerous and spread in every road and alley until it was said that they amounted to about 50,000 donkeys that are rented every day in Egypt, As for horses, only soldiers and soldiers can ride them. They also extract oil from radishes and turnips, and they call it hot oil. As for olive oil, it is abundant and cheap, in order to light lamps in roads and corridors. It is noticeable that Egypt's merchants are extremely rich and affluent, and this is what happened in the year 439 AH when, The Sultan was blessed with a boy, as the decorations were announced in the city and the markets and they held celebrations for the new born, so that the sellers of clothes and fabrics and the money changers decorated their stores with gold, precious gems and types of luxurious fabrics of brocade silk (Zaki Muhammad Hassan, 2008, pg. 49 and Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 120-121), This is evidence of the enormous wealth that Egypt reached in that period.

3- Industry:

As for industries, there are many industries in which precise tools are used, the most important of which are the manufacture of bowls, combs and scissors, as well as making crystal, which is very beautiful, and there are many craftsmen who carve this crystal with high skill, and there is also ivory that is brought from Zanzibar, Manufacture of shoes from cowhide, including the manufacture of honey and sugar (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, pp. 107-108, Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 118, and Muhammad Jamal, 1994, p. 136)

As for the ceramics industry, which is considered one of the important and delicate industries, and it is a sophisticated industry, so that if a person puts his hand in one side of the porcelain, he sees it from the other side.

They use porcelain in the manufacture of cups and dishes, and paint them in beautiful colors, such as the tail of a peacock, and they make jugs from it that are clear as peridot and are sold by weight as if they are gold (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 118-119 and Nasir Khusraw, 1983, pp. 108-109).

One of the most important aspects of life for sellers and market merchants is that they are famous for their honesty in dealings, and if one of them lies, he is punished by ordering to ride a camel and give him a bell in his hand, and he roams the city while calling saying, "I have lied, and here I am punishing, and whoever tells the lie will be punished." (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 120 and Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 109-110).

Army:

Then he talked about the number of the army of al-Mu'izz li-Din Allah with which he crossed the Nile, which is estimated at about 30 thousand fighters with full equipment, all of them from the Mamluks of the Sultan, They came and Al-Moez came with his entourage on board the ships that arrived in Cairo, then he ordered their evacuation to be presented to the people and be a memory, and these ships remained in place for about 80 years. Then he describes the arrival of Caliph Al-Mu'izz li-Din Allah with his army in Cairo and his reception by the Fatimid leader Jawhar Al-Siqilli.

Cairo was called by this name in reference to the army of al-Mu'izz li-Din Allah, the Fatimid al-Qahir who resided there, Al-Moez prevented the army from entering Cairo so that people would not be harmed (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 94, and Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 103).

The number of workers in the Sultan's palace is also estimated at about 12,000 servants, as for the women and maidservants, no one knows their number. The palace has 10 doors for each door with a name known to it. Under the palace there is a secret door for the Sultan that exits from it when he leaves the palace, and he has another palace outside Cairo and is connected to the other palace Underground tunnels and corridors (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 104-105, Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 95, Zaki Muhammad Hassan, 2009, p. 23).

Then he touches on social life in Cairo, especially the drinking of wine, which was strictly forbidden, as women were not allowed to go out naked, and the circulation of raisins was prohibited so that they would not be made into wine (Nasir Khusraw, 1983, p. 95, and Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, p. 105).

Gulf Opening Day:

Nasir Khusraw also provides a beautiful description of the celebration of the feast of the conquest of the Gulf, and the Gulf is a watercourse in the vicinity of Cairo, it starts in Egypt and ends in Cairo and revolves around it and passes in front of the Sultan's Palace. Two palaces were built on its head – the first was called the Pearl Palace, and the second was called the Jewel Palace, and he says that when the Nile floods during the winter season, the expenses and canals are closed, then the Sultan comes to open this river at the mouth of The Gulf, this day is known (the day the Sultan rides to open the Gulf) It is one of the greatest feasts in Egypt, where preparations take place three days before this feast, and a very large tent is erected, decorated and made of Rumi silk, embroidered with gold and peacock tapestry.

The knights line up about a thousand horsemen with their horses saddled with golden saddles and beautifully decorated quilts, On these scrolls, the name of the Sultan is written in gold water, and behind the cavalry the team of the Jamaliyat line up with its full adornment, and behind the Jamaliah a team that rides on mules and is studded with precious jewels, The Sultan's army will come out as a whole, and it is made up of several divisions, The first group, called the Kitamites, came from Kairouan, and their number was estimated at twenty thousand horsemen.

Then the (Batilin) group, who are from Morocco, numbering about fifteen thousand horsemen, and a third group, which is the (Al-Masamadah) group, their color is black, and their number is estimated at twenty thousand men, and a fourth group is called (Al-Masharqa).

And they are Turks and non-Arabs, and because of their claim that they are not Arabs, and their number is estimated at ten thousand men, and another group is called (Ubaid al-Shura') and they are bought slaves, and their number is estimated at thirty thousand men, and a group called (Bedouins) who are from the people of the Hijaz and their number is estimated at fifty thousand horsemen.

And another group called (Al-Ustadhiyin) or (Al-Qasryoon) attributed to the royal palace, and all of them are white and black servants, bought for service, and they have a special military commander, and their number is estimated at thirty thousand knights.

There is another group of sons of the royal families, who came from outside the country to participate in the feasts and conquest of the Gulf, and they are not included in the census of the Sultan's army (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 108-111, and Nasir Khusraw, 1983, pp. 97-100, Zaki Muhammad Hassan, 2009, p. 24 and see Hassan Khudairy Ahmed, 1996, pp. 284-285).

On the morning of the opening of the Gulf, the Sultan comes with ten thousand men, and in front of them is music, drums, and flutes, A large gathering of scholars and the pillars of the state, and after the Sultan reached the mouth of the Gulf, He rests for an hour, then brings a piece of wood to open the Gulf Wall, marking its official opening, Then the dam breaks and the water begins to flow, Then the ululations and chants rise, And gather around the Gulf many people, The Sultan gives charity to the people with money and gifts. The royal palace is surrounded by twenty-one boats in the waters of the Gulf, fifty cubits long and twenty cubits wide, loaded with precious jewels (Nasir Khosrow Alawi, 1993, pp. 111-113, Nasir Khusraw, 1983, pp. 101-103, and Hassan Khudairi Ahmed, 1996, p. 286).

science and teaching:

As for knowledge and teaching, it was one of the prominent features of Egypt at that time, as permanent lessons were held in mosques.

The courtyards of the mosques are lit with lamps of silver, each of which weighs a hundred pounds, and the mosque of Amr ibn al-Aas is furnished with mats with ten colored plates.

The mosque is lit by more than a hundred lanterns every night, and there is a market on the northern side of the mosque called (Suq al-Qanadeel), as this market contains antiques, anecdotes and valuables from all parts of the world (Nasir Khusraw Alawi, 1993, pp. 117-118, Muhammad Jamal Surur, 1994, p. 140, and Nasir Khusraw, 1983, pp. 106-107).

Results:**The study concluded several results, including:**

1. The traveler grew up in a turbulent political environment in the Islamic East at the end of the fourth century AH and the beginning of the fifth century AH.
2. The religious motive was one of the most important motives for this journey, which leads man to the sound faith by visiting Mecca to perform the Hajj.
3. This trip reflected the clear civilized and humanitarian vision of the social and economic life of the country to which the traveler arrived.
4. Admiration and approval of Egypt through his trip to the Egyptian lands, until he prepared it as a model for the virtuous city headed by the just ruler who does not oppress anyone.
5. Progress and prosperity in trade and industry in Egypt in that period, especially the textile industry and turbans that were woven from colored reeds, as Nasir Khusraw considered it the first free trade city in the world in that period.
6. The importance of the Nile River in the lives of the Egyptians, and that Egypt is the gift of the Nile, as it was based on the advanced Egyptian agriculture and industry.

7. It also describes the construction of Cairo and the role of the Fatimid devotees of God in building it, the military forces that entered with al-Mu'izz and their numbers, religious monuments, mosques and monasteries, and the civilizational progress in building castles, forts and tall buildings.
8. A description of the economic life in Egypt, including shops, alleys, and multi-purpose markets, which were crowded with pedestrians, merchants, buying and selling, which indicates an active economic life in that period, in addition to a description of the scientific and teaching life and educational activity in the permanent seminars that are held in mosques where student's writers and readers.

References

The Holy Quran

- Abu Mu'in al-Din Nasir Khusraw al-Qabadani al-Marwazi: Safarnama, the journey of Nasir Khusraw al-Qabadani, translated and presented by Ahmad Khalid al-Abdali, King Saud University, i 1, 1983 AD.
- Alice Hensberger: Nasir Khusraw Yaqouta in Badakhshan, translated by Saif al-Din al-Qusayr, Dar al-Mada for Culture and Publishing, Damascus, 1, 2003 AD.
- Hassan Khudairi Ahmed: Relations of the Fatimids in Egypt with the Countries of the Maghreb (362-567 AH) Madbouly Library, Cairo, 1st Edition, 1996 AD.
- Zaki Muhammed Hassan: Muslim Travelers in the Middle Ages, The Nabilities of Thought Company, Cairo, 1, 2008 AD.
- Zaki Muhammad Hassan: The Fatimid Treasures, Nawabigh Al-Fikr Company, 1st Edition, Cairo, 2009 AD.
- Abdulaziz Salem: The History of Islamic Egypt until the End of the Fatimid Era, University Youth Foundation, Alexandria, 2001 AD.
- Nasir Khusraw Abu Moin: The Mosque of the Two Wisdoms, translated from Persian by Ibrahim Al-Desouki Sheta, Dar Al-Thaqafa for Printing and Publishing, Cairo, 1974 AD.
- Nasser Khosrow Alawi: Safarnama, translated by Yahya Al-Khashab, foreword by Abdel Wahab Al-Azzam, the Egyptian General Book Organization, 2nd edition, 1993.
- Muhammad Jamal Sorour: History of the Fatimid State, Dar al-Fikr al-Arabi, Egypt, 1994 AD.

Author Information

Dr. Ibrahim Ahmad Al Shyyab

Dr. Abeer Mansour ALkhasawneh

Dr. RiyadMoflehALkhlaifat
